

An Overview of Contact Mechanics Algorithms

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2024

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In both technological applications and natural processes, the behavior of moving boundaries between different media plays a crucial role. The development of algorithms to solve problems involving these dynamic boundaries is a primary objective in continuum mechanics. This review focuses on the evolution of contact algorithms, which are integral components of numerical methods in continuum mechanics, responsible for determining, tracking, and computing interactions at contact, interphase, and moving free boundaries.

Classification of Contact Algorithms

One way to classify contact algorithms is by the method used to describe the motion of a continuous medium. In Lagrangian algorithms, nodes move with the velocity of the material medium, making them well-suited for problems where material boundaries need to be explicitly tracked. Conversely, in non-Lagrangian algorithms, nodes either remain stationary, as seen in Eulerian algorithms, or move independently of the material medium, as in arbitrary Eulerian-Lagrangian (ALE) algorithms. Non-Lagrangian algorithms are characterized by the inclusion of convective terms in their evolution equations, which arise from the difference in velocities between the coordinates and the medium.

Another classification approach is based on how the boundaries are identified and tracked. In both Eulerian and Lagrangian frameworks, moving boundaries can be explicitly tracked using algorithms that identify them as a set of surface nodes (markers) and cells. Alternatively, boundaries can be implicitly determined using capturing algorithms that employ continuous marker functions. This classification serves as the foundation for systematizing the literature on contact algorithms, aligning with modern trends in synthesizing methods from deformable media mechanics and hydrodynamics to construct integrated mathematical models of technological and natural processes.

Types of Boundaries Considered

In addition to the classical formulations of initial boundary value problems in continuum mechanics, contact problems introduce special boundary conditions that control the motion of boundary surfaces and potential singularities. For classical contact problems, these conditions express the non-penetration constraint, Newton's law of action and reaction, and the law of surface friction. The normal projections of these conditions prevent the mutual penetration of immiscible media, while the tangential projections account for the frictional forces between contacting surfaces.

The extended physical formulation includes additional contact boundary conditions for phenomena such as heat transfer, electromagnetic interaction, diffusion, and chemical reactions. These formulations also address related cases of boundary conditions that describe the behavior of free and interphase boundaries. Free boundaries exist between condensed (liquid or solid) and rarefied media, with boundary conditions describing the influence of external pressure, friction, and surface tension forces, which depend on the orientation and curvature of the boundary.

Unlike classical contact and free boundaries, interphase boundaries are not Lagrangian. Their motion within a continuous medium is governed by interphase equilibrium conditions, such as Stefan's law for phase changes, the Chapman–Jouguet condition for detonations, or plasticity and failure criteria. Interphase boundaries represent surfaces of weak discontinuity, moving through the medium while tracking phase transitions that involve abrupt changes in material properties. At these boundaries, temperature, velocity vectors, displacements, and stresses remain continuous, whereas properties like heat capacity and compressibility can change abruptly.

A significant special case within contact problems involves the interaction of deformable media with absolutely rigid bodies. This scenario simplifies certain aspects of the problem, as the rigid body's motion is either predetermined or calculated within the broader context of the problem, considering factors such as mass and reaction forces.

Formulations of Contact Problems

Initial-value contact problems can be formulated using differential, integral, or variational approaches. Variational formulations, particularly those involving variational inequalities, are crucial for studying the correctness of initial-value problems and for establishing the existence and uniqueness of solutions. Significant contributions to the study of these formulations include the works of Signorini, and Stampacchia, among others, who have explored various aspects of contact problem formulations. Technical studies have also examined the application of these formulations to problems involving phase transitions.

Lagrangian Algorithms for Rigid Body Contact

A substantial portion of the literature on contact problems focuses on scenarios involving deformable bodies interacting with absolutely rigid bodies, such as stamps, strikers, or barriers. In these cases, the moving boundary of the rigid body is treated as a predetermined sliding surface, which may be either smooth or rough. The motion of the rigid body is either assumed or computed within the overall problem, using methods from theoretical mechanics that account for mass and reaction forces.

In Lagrangian grid contact algorithms, boundary velocities between rigid and deformable bodies are either specified or adjusted based on the penetration of grid nodes into prohibited regions representing rigid bodies. Normal velocity and displacement components are corrected to prevent numerical penetration. When external normal loads are applied during correction, contact pressure can be determined, while friction is handled similarly to other contact algorithms.

Lagrangian End-to-End Algorithms

Lagrangian end-to-end algorithms use a single Lagrangian grid across contacting media, sharing common nodes at the interface. In these algorithms, the solution is continuous across the contact boundary, with contact discontinuities modeled by narrow zones of large solution gradients. This approach is particularly effective for small deformations and known contact

zones, where the contact conditions can approximate complete adhesion, leading to ideal contact scenarios.

In cases of large deformations and dynamic contact zones, step-by-step automated correction of buffer layers is required. These buffer elements or contact pairs are redefined during the numerical solution process, with contact reactions determined by satisfying contact conditions at the grid level. For complex scenarios involving multiple contacts, models and algorithms for end-to-end contact boundary calculations become essential, especially in the study of composite materials with heterogeneous subregions.

Algorithms for Searching Contact Zones

In Lagrangian grid methods, body boundaries are represented by boundary surface cells. The contact zone, often unknown in advance, must be identified during calculations. This search is performed by detecting the penetration or convergence of boundary nodes and cells, resulting in a list of contact pairs that facilitate automated construction of contact or buffer elements. However, the computational cost increases with the number of boundary cells or nodes, necessitating the use of optimized algorithms for accelerated contact zone search.

Eulerian Algorithms for Contact Boundaries

When dealing with processes where multiple regions of material phase are united, describing these scenarios with Lagrangian methods can be challenging, especially in three dimensions. Eulerian and Arbitrary Eulerian-Lagrangian (ALE) algorithms offer solutions by eliminating the need for constant updates of boundary node lists and overcoming time step restrictions due to node convergence. These algorithms are particularly useful for processes like fragmentation, where tracking interphase boundaries through Lagrangian methods is impractical.

Review of Eulerian Algorithms

Eulerian methods that implement continuous tracking of contact discontinuities have developed into a robust set of algorithms with their own rich literature. These methods are critical for handling complex contact scenarios and are often reviewed separately due to their extensive application in various fields.

Statement of a three-dimensional of nonlinear deformation of elastic-plastic bodies

Here a deformable solid body of volume V_0 , considered by a boundary surface S_0 , be related to an orthogonal Cartesian coordinate system x^i ($i = 1, 2, 3$). For the stress vectors σ_i^* on the areas of the deformed elementary volume, related to units of area, dS_0 and volume dV_0 , we can adopt the expansions, $\sigma_i^* = \sigma_{ij}^* \mathbf{R}_j^*$ where $\mathbf{R}_i^* = \partial \mathbf{R}^* / \partial x^i = \mathbf{e}_i + \mathbf{u}_{,i}$ are the main basis vectors in the deformed state of the body, $\mathbf{u}$ is the displacement vector. The quantities σ_{ij}^* , which are contravariant components of the symmetric tensor of conditional stresses, according

to V.V. Novozhilov are called generalized stresses. In addition, for the vectors of generalized stresses σ_i^* we can adopt the representations, $\sigma_i^* = s_{ij}^* e_j$ where, as is easy to show,

$$s_{ij}^* = \sigma_{ik}^* (\delta_{kj} + e_{kj}) \quad (1)$$

We will call the true deformations of elongations ε_i and shears $\sin \gamma_{ij}$ the quantities

$$\begin{aligned} \varepsilon_{ii}^{tr} &= \varepsilon_i = dl_i^* / dl_i - 1 = \sqrt{1 + 2\varepsilon_{ii}} - 1, \\ \varepsilon_{ij}^{tr} &= \sin \gamma_{ij} = 2\varepsilon_{ij} (1 + 2\varepsilon_{ii})^{-\frac{1}{2}} (1 + 2\varepsilon_{jj})^{-\frac{1}{2}} = \\ &= 2\varepsilon_{ij} (1 + \varepsilon_i)^{-1} (1 + \varepsilon_j)^{-1} \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

and the true stresses, $\sigma_{ij} \neq \sigma_{ji}$ related to units of deformed areas, S_i^* according to Novozhilov, are the components of vectors σ_i in the representations $\sigma_i = \sigma_{ij} e_j^*$, where $e_j^* = R_j^* / |R_j^*| = (1 + \varepsilon_j)^{-1} (\delta_{ji} + e_{ji}) e_i$ are unit vectors directed along tangents to the deformed coordinate lines at the point $M^*(x^i)$, into which the point passes after deformation $M(x^i)$.

It is known that during plastic deformation under complex loading conditions, the relationships between stresses and strains, which are used in the theory of elasticity, are replaced in the theory of plastic flow by relationships between strain and stress increments. It is assumed that there is a yield condition that determines the stress state, when fulfilled, the infinitely close vicinity of a material point is deformed plastically.

When using the yield condition in the Prandtl-Reuss equations it can be written in terms of the increments of true stresses and true strains.

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta \sigma_{ij} &= \frac{E}{1 - 2\mu} \delta_{ij} \Delta \varepsilon_0^{tr} + 2G \Delta \varepsilon_{ij}^{tr} - \alpha \frac{3G \sum_{k,l} \sigma'_{kl} \Delta \varepsilon_{kl}^{tr}}{(\sigma_i)^2 (H'_\chi / 3G + 1)} \sigma'_{ij} = \\ &= D_{ijmn} \Delta e_{mn} + D_{ij}^p (\Delta e_{mn}, e_{mn}), \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

For elastic-plastic bodies with isotropic hardening, where only the scalar hardening parameter is selected as the internal parameters of state associated with plastic deformation and describing the structural changes that have arisen in the material, χ^* the yield condition through the components of true stresses σ_{ij} is formulated as:

$$F^* \equiv \sigma_i^* - c^* = \sigma_i^* - H^*(\chi^*) = 0 \quad (4)$$

where σ_i^* is the intensity of true stresses, H is a monotonically increasing positive function approximating the true deformation diagram of the material. In what follows, we adopt the notation for true deformations of the form:

$$\varepsilon_{ii}^{tr} = \varepsilon_i, \varepsilon_{ij}^{tr} = \sin \gamma_{ij} \text{ in case of } i \neq j \quad (5)$$

and we will select the linear part in them (the tensor of small deformations for small displacements) according to the concepts

$$\begin{aligned} \varepsilon_{ii}^{tr} &= e_{ii} + \left(\sqrt{1 + 2\varepsilon_{ii}} - 1 - e_{ii} \right) = e_{ii} + e_{ii}^{nl}, \\ \varepsilon_{ij}^{tr} &= e_{ij} + \left(2\varepsilon_{ij} (1 + 2\varepsilon_{ii})^{-\frac{1}{2}} (1 + 2\varepsilon_{jj})^{-\frac{1}{2}} - e_{ij} \right) = e_{ij} + e_{ij}^{nl}, \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

In equations (3), $\Delta\varepsilon_{ij}^{tr}$ the increments of the strain components $\Delta\varepsilon_{ij}^{tr}$ are denoted by $\Delta\varepsilon_0^{tr}$, the increments of the average true strain are denoted by $\Delta\varepsilon_{ij}^{tr}$, the increments of the deviator of true strains are denoted by D_{ijmn} and $D_{ij}^p(e_{mn}, \Delta e_{mn})$ the linear elastic constants of the material and the nonlinear part of the stress increment are denoted by α and β , where

$$\begin{aligned} \alpha &= 1, \text{ if } \sigma_i - c = 0 \text{ и } \sum_{i,j} \sigma_{ij} \Delta\varepsilon_{ij}^{tr} \geq 0, \\ \alpha &= 0, \text{ if } \sigma_i - c < 0 \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

$$\sigma_i - c = 0 \text{ and } \sum_{i,j} \sigma_{ij} \Delta\varepsilon_{ij}^{tr} < 0$$

Algorithm for the process of continuing the solution of a variational problem with respect to a parameter. The variational equation of the principle of possible displacements can be written as:

$$\iiint_{V_0} \sigma_{ij}^* \delta\varepsilon_{ij} dV_0 = \iiint_{V_0} F_i^* \delta u^i dV_0 + \iint_{S_0} P_i^* \delta u^i dS_0 \quad (8)$$

where P^* and F^* are the vectors of stresses, surface and volume forces on the areas of the deformed elementary volume, referred to units of area dS_0 and volume dV_0 .

According to the method used, which is ideally suited for solving elastic-plastic problems in flow theory and is called the “globally incremental Lagrange theory”, the deformation process is represented as a sequence of equilibrium states at corresponding loading levels:

$$\left({}^1F_i^*, {}^1P_i^*\right), \left({}^2F_i^*, {}^2P_i^*\right), \dots, \left({}^lF_i^*, {}^lP_i^*\right), \dots \quad (9)$$

In this case, it is assumed that some l state is known, i.e. the displacements ${}^l u^i$, components of the Cauchy-Green strain tensor ${}^l \varepsilon_{ij}$, true strains ${}^l \varepsilon_{ij}^{tr}$ and stresses satisfying the variational equation of the principle of possible displacements are found

$$\begin{aligned} \delta^l \mathcal{D} &= \iiint_{V_l} {}^l s_{ij}^* \delta^l e_{ij} dV_l - {}^l R = 0, \\ {}^l R &= \iiint_{V_l} {}^l F_i^* \delta^l u^i dV_l + \iint_{S_l} {}^l P_i^* \delta^l u^i dS_l \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

the equilibrium equations that follow from it

$$f_i^* ({}^l u^i) + {}^l F_i^* = 0 \quad (11)$$

and the corresponding static or kinematic boundary conditions formulated under hard kinematic loading of samples.

If the loads acting on the body receive increments $\Delta {}^l F_i^*, \Delta {}^l P_i^*$, then all points of the body receive displacement increments $\Delta {}^l u^i$, which must satisfy the variational equation for the $(l+1)$ state of the form:

$$\begin{aligned} \delta^{l+1} \mathcal{D} &= \iiint_{V_l} ({}^l s_{ij}^* + \Delta {}^l s_{ij}^*) \delta \Delta^l e_{ij} dV_l - \\ &- \iiint_{V_l} ({}^l F_i^* + \Delta {}^l F_i^*) \delta \Delta^l u^i dV_l - \iint_{S_l} ({}^l P_i^* + \Delta {}^l P_i^*) \delta \Delta^l u^i dS_l, \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

$$\text{for the } (l+1)\text{- } \delta^l u^i = 0, \delta^l e_{ij} = 0, \delta^l \varepsilon_{ij} = 0 \quad (13)$$

For further transformation of equation (12), the relations connecting the generalized and true stresses are represented in the form

$$\sigma_{ii}^* = \sigma_{ii} (1 + f_{ii}(e_{km})), \sigma_{ij}^* = \sigma_{ij} (1 + f_{ij}(e_{km})), \quad (14)$$

where

$$f_{11} = \frac{(1 + \varepsilon_2)(1 + \varepsilon_3) \cos \gamma_{23}}{1 + \varepsilon_1} - 1, f_{12} = (1 + \varepsilon_3) \cos \gamma_{23} - 1, \quad \overline{1,2,3} \quad (15)$$

When using relations (14), the left side of equation (12) allows the following transformations

$$\begin{aligned} \iiint_{V_l} ({}^l s_{ij}^* + \Delta {}^l s_{ij}^*) \delta \Delta {}^l e_{ij} dV_l &= \iiint_{V_l} ({}^l \sigma_{ik}^* + \Delta {}^l \sigma_{ik}^*) (\delta_{kj} + {}^l e_{kj} + \Delta {}^l e_{kj}) \cdot \\ \cdot \delta \Delta {}^l e_{ij} dV_l &= \iiint_{V_l} \underline{({}^l \sigma_{ik} + \Delta {}^l \sigma_{ik}) (1 + f_{ik} + \Delta f_{ik})} (\delta_{kj} + {}^l e_{kj} + \Delta {}^l e_{kj}) \cdot \\ \cdot \delta \Delta {}^l e_{ij} dV_l &= \iiint_{V_l} \underline{({}^l \sigma_{ik} + D_{ikrs} \Delta {}^l e_{rs} + D_{ik}^a (\Delta {}^l e_{mn}, {}^l e_{mn}))} \cdot \\ \cdot (1 + f_{ik} + \Delta f_{ik}) (\delta_{kj} + {}^l e_{kj} + \Delta {}^l e_{kj}) \delta \Delta {}^l e_{ij} dV_l, \end{aligned} \quad (16)$$

where in the underlined expressions there is no summation over the indices i and k .

Substituting this equality into (12) yields the equation

$$\begin{aligned} \iiint_{V_l} D_{ikrs} \Delta {}^l e_{rs} \delta \Delta {}^l e_{ij} dV_l + \iiint_{V_l} \underline{{}^l \sigma_{ik} (1 + f_{ik} + \Delta f_{ik}) \Delta {}^l e_{kj}} \delta \Delta {}^l e_{ij} dV_l &= \\ = {}^l R + \Delta {}^l R - \iiint_{V_l} \underline{{}^l \sigma_{ik} (1 + f_{ik})} (\delta_{kj} + {}^l e_{kj}) \delta \Delta {}^l e_{ij} dV_l - \\ - \iiint_{V_l} \underline{\sigma_{ik} \Delta f_{ik}} (\delta_{kj} + {}^l e_{kj}) \delta \Delta {}^l e_{ij} dV_l - \\ - \iiint_{V_l} \underline{D_{ik}^a (\Delta {}^l e_{mn}, {}^l e_{mn}) (1 + f_{ik} + \Delta f_{ik})} (\delta_{kj} + {}^l e_{kj} + \Delta {}^l e_{kj}) \cdot \\ \cdot \delta \Delta {}^l e_{ij} dV_l - \iiint_{V_l} \underline{D_{ikrs} \Delta {}^l e_{rs} (f_{ik} + \Delta f_{ik})} (\delta_{kj} + {}^l e_{kj} + \Delta {}^l e_{kj}) \cdot \\ \cdot \delta \Delta {}^l e_{ij} dV_l - \iiint_{V_l} D_{ikrs} \Delta {}^l e_{rs} ({}^l e_{kj} + \Delta {}^l e_{kj}) \delta \Delta {}^l e_{ij} dV_l \end{aligned} \quad (17)$$

which in abbreviated form can be represented as:

$$\begin{aligned} \iiint_{V_l} D_{ikrs} \Delta {}^l e_{rs} \delta \Delta {}^l e_{ij} dV_l + \iiint_{V_l} \underline{{}^l \sigma_{ik} (1 + f_{ik} + \Delta f_{ik}) \Delta {}^l e_{kj}} \delta \Delta {}^l e_{ij} dV_l &= \\ = {}^l R + \Delta {}^l R - \iiint_{V_l} \underline{{}^l \sigma_{ik} (1 + f_{ik})} (\delta_{kj} + {}^l e_{kj}) \delta \Delta {}^l e_{ij} dV_l - \\ - \iiint_{V_l} \underline{\sigma_{ik} \Delta f_{ik}} (\delta_{kj} + {}^l e_{kj}) \delta \Delta {}^l e_{ij} dV_l - A^a ({}^l e_{mn}, \Delta {}^l e_{mn}) \end{aligned} \quad (18)$$

In the right-hand side of this equation, the second term of the left-hand side and the first with the third term of the right-hand side represent the same variational equation (10) for the l -state, in which, instead of variation, the possible displacements are variations of increments $\delta\Delta^l u^i$. Since at the l -loading step, equation (10) is performed with some error when organizing calculations, these terms are usually retained in the resolving equation (18), which ensures greater accuracy in solving problems. The remaining terms of the right-hand side of equation (16) with factors at the σ_{ik} first loading step are equal to zero due to ${}^l\sigma_{ik} = 0$, and the terms combined under the operator $A^a({}^l e_{nm}, \Delta^l e_{nm})$, under the assumption that the displacement increments at the loading step are small, are small compared to the rest. When they are discarded at each loading step, a system of linear equations is obtained for determining $\Delta^l u^i$ in the form:

$$\begin{aligned} & \iiint_{V_l} D_{ikrs} \Delta^l e_{rs} \delta\Delta^l e_{ij} dV_l + \iiint_{V_l} \frac{{}^l\sigma_{ik} (1 + f_{ik} + \Delta f_{ik})}{\Delta^l e_{ij}} \Delta^l e_{kj} \delta\Delta^l e_{ij} dV_l = \\ & = {}^l R + \Delta^l R - \iiint_{V_l} \frac{{}^l\sigma_{ik} (1 + f_{ik})}{\Delta^l e_{ij}} (\delta_{kj} + {}^l e_{kj}) \delta\Delta^l e_{ij} dV_l - \\ & - \iiint_{V_l} \frac{{}^l\sigma_{ik} \Delta f_{ik}}{\Delta^l e_{ij}} (\delta_{kj} + {}^l e_{kj}) \delta\Delta^l e_{ij} dV_l \end{aligned} \quad (19)$$

and at the first loading step ${}^l\sigma_{ik} = 0$. The transition to the next loading step involves calculations

$$\begin{aligned} & {}^{l+1}u^i = {}^l u^i + \Delta^l u^i, \quad \Delta^l \sigma_{ij} = D_{ijks} \Delta^l e_{ks} + D_{ij}^a(e_{mn}, \Delta e_{mn}) \\ & {}^{l+1}\sigma_{ij} = {}^l \sigma_{ij} + B_l^{l+1}(\Delta^l \sigma_{ij}), \quad {}^{l+1}R = {}^l R + \Delta^l R \end{aligned} \quad (20)$$

Where $B_l^{l+1}(\Delta^l \sigma_{ij})$ is the transition operator of the stress increment components from $(l+1)$ the - state to the l , and the stresses ${}^{l+1}\sigma_{ij}$ are written in the basis of the l state. In this case, it is necessary to carry out an iterative refinement in order to take into account the terms in equation A^a (19). The corresponding equation will have the form:

$$\begin{aligned}
& \iiint_{V_l} D_{ikrs} \Delta^l e_{rs} \delta \Delta^l e_{ij} dV_l + \iiint_{V_l} \frac{{}^l \sigma_{ik}^{(q)} (1 + f_{ik} + \Delta f_{ik}) \Delta^l e_{kj}^{(q)} \delta \Delta^l e_{ij} dV_l = \\
& = {}^l R + \Delta^l R - \iiint_{V_l} \frac{{}^l \sigma_{ik}^{(q)} (1 + f_{ik}) (\delta_{kj} + {}^l e_{kj}^{(q)}) \delta \Delta^l e_{ij} dV_l - \iiint_{V_l} \frac{\sigma_{ik}^{(q)}}{{}^l \sigma_{ik}^{(q)}} \cdot \\
& \cdot \frac{\Delta f_{ik} (\delta_{kj} + {}^l e_{kj}^{(q)}) \delta \Delta^l e_{ij} dV_l - \iiint_{V_l} \frac{D_{ik}^a (\Delta^l e_{mn}, {}^l e_{mn}) (1 + f_{ik} + \Delta f_{ik}) \cdot}{D_{ik}^a (\Delta^l e_{mn}, {}^l e_{mn}) (1 + f_{ik} + \Delta f_{ik})} \cdot \\
& \cdot (\delta_{kj} + {}^l e_{kj}^{(q)} + \Delta^l e_{kj}^{(q)}) \delta \Delta^l e_{ij} dV_l - \iiint_{V_l} \frac{D_{ikrs} \Delta^l e_{rs}^{(q)} (f_{ik} + \Delta f_{ik}) (\delta_{kj} + \\
& + {}^l e_{kj}^{(q)} + \Delta^l e_{kj}^{(q)}) \delta \Delta^l e_{ij} dV_l - \iiint_{V_l} D_{ikrs} \Delta^l e_{rs}^{(q)} ({}^l e_{kj}^{(q)} + \Delta^l e_{kj}^{(q)}) \delta \Delta^l e_{ij} dV_l
\end{aligned} \tag{21}$$

where q is the iteration number. And the transition to the next iteration involves the following calculations

$$\begin{aligned}
\Delta^l u_{(q+1)}^i &= \Delta^l u_{(q)}^i + \Delta^l u, \Delta^l \sigma_{ij}^{(q+1)} = D_{ijks} \Delta^l e_{ks}^{(q)} + D_{ij}^a (e_{mn}^{(q)}, \Delta e_{mn}^{(q)}), \\
{}^l \sigma_{ij}^{(q+1)} &= {}^l \sigma_{ij}^{(q)} + B_l^{l+1} (\Delta^l \sigma_{ij}^{(q+1)})
\end{aligned} \tag{22}$$

The transition to the next step involves recalculating the stress ${}^{l+1} \sigma_{ij}$ in $(l+1)$ the basis state.

Modeling of mechanical contact

To implement the mechanism of interaction of elements of deformable structures with each other, a special contact layer with specific properties is introduced. This can be either a real gasket between the contacting surfaces or a fictitious contact layer, but having a certain finite thickness. Depending on the nature of external effects on the contacting surfaces, various options for their interaction are possible.

Case a) assumes that under the action of an external load the contacting surfaces are pressed against each other and in the contact layer (finite element) a compression stress $\sigma_H = \sigma_A = \sigma_B$ and deformation $\varepsilon_H = \sigma_H / E_H$ arise, where E_H is the modulus of elasticity of the contact layer material, σ_A and σ_B are the normal stresses on the contacting surfaces. The geometric condition for the occurrence of such a variant of deformation of the contact layer is $H \leq H_0$, where H_0 is the initial thickness of the contact layer, H is the distance between the contacting surfaces.

Case b) occurs in the presence of preliminary compression, when $H \leq H_0$ the external load is such that the contacting surfaces diverge but do not break away from each other. In this case, the following relations are also valid:

$$\sigma_H = \sigma_A = \sigma_B, \varepsilon_H = \sigma_H / E_H \tag{23}$$

In the case of separation of the contacting surfaces, the following relations are valid:

$$H \geq H_0, \quad \sigma_H = 0 \quad (24)$$

Case c) illustrates free slip, in which shear stresses do not arise. This variant of interaction arises at $H \geq H_0$, and in this case $\tau_H = 0$.

Case d) is characterized by a variant of elastic deformation of the contact layer with compression and shear without slipping. This situation occurs when $H \leq H_0$, and the following relations are valid for stresses and deformations in the pads:

$$\sigma_H = \sigma_A = \sigma_B, \quad \tau_H = \tau_A = \tau_B, \quad \varepsilon_H = \sigma_H / E_H, \quad \gamma_H = \tau_H / G_H, \quad (25)$$

but in this case an additional condition must be met

$$\tau_H \leq f |\sigma_H|, \quad (26)$$

where f is the linear coefficient of friction.

Alternatively:

$$\sigma_H = \sigma^A = \sigma^B, \quad \tau_H = \tau_{np} = f |\sigma_H|, \quad \varepsilon_H = \frac{\sigma_H}{E_H}. \quad (27)$$

and there is a possibility of slippage.

All these deformation variants can be modeled within the framework of solid mechanics by introducing a certain contact layer with specific properties. In particular, the relationship between normal compression stresses σ_H and transverse deformations

$$\varepsilon = \frac{H - H_0}{H_0}, \quad (28)$$

should have the form shown in Figure 1. a), and the relationship between shear stresses τ_H and shear strains γ should be in the form of a diagram in Figure 1. b), where both loading and unloading processes are depicted.

Fig.1 Relationships between stresses and strains in the contact layer: a – for normal components; b – for tangential components.

Naturally, the limiting values of shear stresses depend on the current compression stresses in the form

$$\tau_{np} = \begin{cases} f |\sigma_H|, & \text{при } \sigma_H < 0 \\ 0, & \text{при } \sigma_H \geq 0 \end{cases}, \quad (29)$$

Thus, we have obtained a nonlinear formulation of the problem of contact interaction of deformable media. A characteristic feature of this problem is that there are limitations on deformation ($H \leq H^A + H^B$), the deformation of the contact layer cannot be greater than its thickness, and for tangential stresses on their limit values, determining the possibility of slippage.

The resolving equation can be written based on the principle of virtual displacements in variational form

$$\begin{aligned} & \sum_m \iiint_{\Omega_m} \{\sigma\}^T \{\delta\varepsilon\} d\Omega + \sum_k \iiint_{\Omega_k} \{\sigma_H\}^T \{\delta\varepsilon_H\} d\Omega = \\ & = \sum_m \left(\iiint_{\Omega_m} \rho \{g\}^T \{\delta V\} d\Omega + \iint_{S_m^\sigma} \{P\}^T \{\delta V\} dS \right), \end{aligned} \quad (30)$$

where the sum over m is the sum over the volumes of the deformable medium, the sum over k is the sum over the volumes of the contact layer, Ω_m, Ω_k are the volumes of the elements of the deformable medium and the contact layer, $\{\sigma\}, \{\varepsilon\}, \{V\}$ respectively; are the stresses, strains and displacements of the deformable medium; $\{\sigma_H\}, \{\varepsilon_H\}$ are the stresses and strains in the contact layer, $\{g\}$ is the acceleration vector of gravity ($\rho \{g\}$ is the force of gravity), $\{P\}$ is the boundary load acting on the part of the boundary S_m^σ .

It is assumed that the compression of the contact layer is initially set, $H_0 < (H^A + H^B)$ is selected as the base case. In the diagrams in Figures 1a) and 1b), these are sections $-1 < \varepsilon_n < 0$ and $-\tau_{np} < \tau < \tau_{np}$, respectively.

To solve the formulated physically nonlinear problem based on equation (30), we will use the iteration method, which is a variant of the initial stress method. The following variational equation is the basis for determining the k- iteration

- where $\tilde{\sigma}_H^k$ is defined as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} & \sum_m \iiint_{\Omega_m} \{\sigma^k\}^T \{\delta\varepsilon\} d\Omega + \sum_k \iiint_{\Omega_k} (\varepsilon_H^k E_H \delta\varepsilon_H + \\ & + \gamma_H^k G_H \delta\gamma_H) d\Omega_k = \sum_m \left(\iiint_{\Omega_m} \rho \{g\}^T (\delta V) d\Omega + \right. \\ & \left. + \iint_{S_m^\sigma} \{p\}^T \{\delta V\} ds \right) + \sum_k \iiint_{\Omega_k} (\tilde{\sigma}_H^k \delta\varepsilon_H + \tilde{\tau}_H^k \delta\gamma_H) d\Omega_k, \end{aligned} \quad (31)$$

- when $-1 \leq \varepsilon_H^k \leq 0$ we accept $\tilde{\sigma}_H^k = 0$ and solve an elastic problem, the real stresses and deformations in the contact layer are determined as:

$$\sigma_H^{P,k} = E_H \varepsilon_H^k, \varepsilon_H^{P,k} = \varepsilon_H^k, \quad (32)$$

- when $\varepsilon_H^k > 0$ we assume $\tilde{\sigma}_H^k = E_H \varepsilon_H^k$ (the “initial stresses” fictitiously introduced into the system for its linearization), the real stresses and deformations in the contact layer are determined as:

$$\sigma_H^{P,k} = 0, \varepsilon_H^{P,k} = \varepsilon_H^k; \quad (33)$$

- when $\varepsilon_H^k < -1$ we consider $\tilde{\sigma}_H^k = E_H (\varepsilon_H^k + 1)$ (stresses from “additional deformations”, also fictitiously introduced), the real stresses and deformations in the contact layer are determined as:

$$\sigma_H^{P,k} = E_H \varepsilon_H^k, \varepsilon_H^{P,k} = -1; \quad (34)$$

ε_H^k deformations determined from the solution of equation (31).

The quantities $\tilde{\tau}_H^k$ in (31) are “initial stresses” and their determination is made as follows:

- the deformations γ_H^k from the solution (31), which are real deformations, are determined;
- the shear stresses are determined $\tau_H^k = G_H \gamma_H^k$ and compared with the maximum permissible ones, we assume

$$\tau_{np}^k = f |\sigma_H^{P,k}|$$

and if, $|\tau_H^k| \leq \tau_{np}^k$ then

$$\tilde{\tau}_H^k = 0,$$

if $|\tau_H^k| \geq \tau_{np}^k$, then

$$\tilde{\tau}_H^k = \tau_H^k - \tau_{np}^k$$

The work also implemented a method for solving this problem in increments, when at the iteration step the unknowns are not the complete displacement fields, which in some situations are fictitious (for $\varepsilon_H < -1$), but their increments.

It is considered that at the initial moment there is some compression $\varepsilon_H^{P,0}$ and, possibly, shear $\gamma_H^{P,0}$, which satisfy the condition.

$$-1 < \varepsilon_H^{P,0} < 0, |G_H \gamma_H^{P,0}| \leq \tau_{np}^0 = f |E_H \varepsilon_H^{P,0}| \quad (35)$$

Then the system of equations (31) is solved for the zero approximation.

$$\begin{aligned} & \sum_m \iiint_{\Omega_m} \{\Delta \sigma^0\}^T \{\delta \varepsilon\} d\Omega + \sum_k \iiint_{\Omega_k} \{\Delta \sigma_H^0\}^T \{\delta \varepsilon_H\} d\Omega = \\ & = \sum_m \left(\iiint_{\Omega_m} \rho \{g\}^T (\delta V) d\Omega + \iint_{S_m^\sigma} \{p\}^T (\delta V) ds \right). \end{aligned} \quad (36)$$

For each subsequent iteration $k=1,2,3,\dots$ the following sequence of calculations is introduced.

We have preliminarily $\{\varepsilon^{k-1}\}, \{\sigma^{k-1}\}$ in the lining blocks, in the contact layer. From the solution of system (31) $\{\varepsilon_H^{P,k-1}\}, \{\sigma_H^{P,k-1}\}, \{\gamma_0^{P,k-1}\}, \{\tau_0^{P,k-1}\}$ at the zero iteration and the equations:

$$\begin{aligned}
& \sum_m \iiint_{\Omega_m} \{\Delta\sigma^k\}^T \{\delta\varepsilon\} d\Omega + \sum_k \iiint_{\Omega_k} \{\Delta\sigma_H^k\}^T \{\delta\varepsilon_H\} d\Omega = \\
& = \sum_k \iiint_{\Omega_k} (\Delta\tilde{\sigma}_H^k \delta\varepsilon_H + \Delta\tilde{\tau}_H^k \delta\gamma_H) d\Omega
\end{aligned} \tag{37}$$

at subsequent iterations, $\{\Delta\varepsilon^k\}, \{\Delta\sigma^k\}, \Delta\varepsilon_H^k, \Delta\gamma_H^k, \Delta\sigma_H^k, \Delta\tau_H^k$ we determine and calculate the next approximation of the stress-strain state of the deformable medium

$$\begin{aligned}
\{\varepsilon^k\} &= \{\varepsilon^{k-1}\} + \{\Delta\varepsilon^{k-1}\}, \\
\{\sigma^k\} &= \{\sigma^{k-1}\} + \{\Delta\sigma^{k-1}\}
\end{aligned} \tag{38}$$

and deformation in the contact layer is:

$$\varepsilon_H^k = \varepsilon_H^{P,k-1} + \Delta\varepsilon_H^{k-1}, \gamma_H^k = \gamma_H^{P,k-1} + \Delta\gamma_H^{k-1}. \tag{39}$$

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